

Geometric Visualization of the $3n + 5$ Problem: Voronoi Tessellation and Six Stable Basins of Attraction in Binary Logarithmic Spiral Space

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Figure 1. Voronoi tessellation of $3n + 5$ orbits in binary logarithmic spiral space. Orbits converging to the 1, 5, 19, 23, 187, or 347 periodic orbits tile the entire space as six distinct color basins.

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